

Dear participant:

We are developing a research to know the relationship between the members of a society and the images that are generated from the new technological media. We would like to have your opinion and is for that we invite you to collaborate in this questionnaire where will be value your visual skills. We remind you that your data will be treated anonymously and will only serve for research purposes.

With your answers we can generate a global map of the visual literacy state in the consumer audience of new technologies. In this way, we can understand how images are produced, perceived, interpreted and received.

Section A: PERSONAL INFORMATION

In this section we ask about your personal characteristics. They help us to know where you come from, who are you or to what generation you belong.

A1. Gender

Female

Male

Other

A2. Age

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A3. Nationality

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A4. Educational level

- Primary education
- Unfinished Compulsory Secondary Education
- Completed Compulsory Secondary Education
- Vocational Training
- University without graduating
- University graduate

Section B: RECEPTION OF IMAGES

About the physical reaction that occurs when light acts on vision and allows the human being to recognize the environment. This ability is common to all of humanity. It has to do with physiology, but also with technology, since the latter is considered a necessary material that allows consuming / receiving those images. In this construct, the learning capacity generated from consumption / reception will be observed.

B1. Classify your degree of vision

- 1. Very bad
- 2. Bad
- 3. Medium
- 4. Good
- 5. Very good

B2. Do you wear glasses or contact lenses?

- Yes
- No

B3. Do you have any visual deficiencies that affect the visual reception of shapes, colors, distances, etc.?

- Yes
- No

B4. If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, indicate which one

C3. If yes, do you usually share the images it produces?

- 1. Never
- 2. Ever
- 3. Most of the time
- 4. Always

C4. When you produce images, how much time do you spend preparing it? (minutes)

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C5. Do you repeat the images until you get the expected result?

- Yes
- No

C6. In your environment, do people who use technology create images and share them?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Sometimes
- 4. Fairly
- 5. Almost always or always

C7. When you share images, do you usually receive them from other people?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Fairly
- 5. Almost always or always

C8. When you share images, do you usually send them to other people?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Fairly
- 5. Almost always or always

C9. When you submit an image, have you treated an image that you have previously received or that has been generated by you?

- 1. I always forward images that send me
- 2. Many times I forward images that send me
- 3. Sometimes I send images that I do and sometimes I do not, the proportion is balanced
- 4. Many times I send images that I do
- 5. I always send images that I do

C10. By reusing an image, can you redefine the message that the sender has thought about?

- Yes
- No
- Do not know / No answer

C11. Do you like to follow people you admire in social networks? Are you a fan or follower of any of them? Do you sometimes write comments in their publications?

- 1. I'm not a fan of anyone I admire
- 2. I am a fan, but you do not interact with their publications
- 3. Sometimes I interact with their publications in the form of like
- 4. I am a fan and I like to interact with them from time to time
- 5. I am a fan and I always make comments in the publications that interest me

C12. When you share images on social networks, do the text companions follow the indications suggested by the applications (labeling, explanation of the image, inspiring text, etc.)?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Quite a few times
- 5. Almost always or always

C13. On the occasion, even being prepared for it, have you stopped attaching images in your messages in social networks, mobile applications, etc., because you do not understand how to do it?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Assez plusieurs fois
- 5. Almost always or always

C14. When you take photos from any of the media at your fingertips, do the process facilitate the options offered by the applications (filter application, cuts, graphic editing, etc.)?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Quite a few times
- 5. Almost always or always

C15. Within your social networks or mobile applications, do you see visual information that you are not looking for (social awareness campaigns, jokes, advertising, etc.)?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Quite a few times
- 5. Almost always or always

C16. If you find that suggested information, what is your attitude?

- 1. I do not access the suggested information
- 2. I access to the suggested information

C17. If you have to create a content presentation...

- 1. I look for images to illustrate what I am saying.
- 2. I generate it

C18. If you look for images in the Internet...

- 1. I search Google Images. I do not consider the license of the image I use
- 2. I search in Google Images. I consider the license of the image I use
- 3. I search in websites specialized on images. I know and use licensed contents

Section D: VISUAL PERCEPTION

This competence is the union of the capture made by the senses and the cultural and emotional baggage of the receiver. A cognitive reaction that relates what is seen with what it means and turns it into a message.

D1. What do you see in this image?

D2. What do you see in this image?

D3. What do you see in this image?

D4. What do you see in this image?

D5. What do you see in this image?

D6. What shape/ shapes do you see in these images?

D7. What shape/ shapes do you see in these images?

D8. What shape/ shapes do you see in these images?

D9. What shape/ shapes do you see in these images?

D10. What shape/ shapes do you see in these images?

D11. What shape/ shapes do you see in these images?

D12. Have you recognized the form/ forms quickly?

Yes

No

Do not know / No answer

D13. In the following image, what catches your attention the most?

D14. In the following image, what catches your attention the most?

D15. In the following image, what catches your attention the most?

D16. In the following image, what catches your attention the most?

D17. What do you see in this image?

D18. What do you see in this image?

D19. What do you see in this image?

D20. What do you see in this image?

D21. What do you see in this image?

D22. What do you see in this image?

D23. What do you see in this image?

D24. Which of the paired images do you find most attractive?

1/2

2/2

1/2

2/2

D25. Which of the paired images do you find most attractive?

1/2

2/2

1/2

2/2

D26. Which of the paired images do you find most attractive?

1/2

2/2

1/2

2/2

D27. Which of the paired images do you find most attractive?

1/2

2/2

1/2

2/2

D28. What do these images suggest to you?

D29. What do these images suggest to you?

D30. What do these images suggest to you?

D31. What do these images suggest to you?

D32. When you receive/ consume images... (select the option / options with which you identify yourself)

- 1. I observe if they are beautiful, harmonic or not
- 2. I wonder if they mean something to me
- 3. I observe the moment and context in which they appear

D33. Point out the differences that exist between these images with your own words

1.

2.

3.

D34. Do you find this image attractive? Why?

D35. Do you find this image attractive? Why?

D36. Do you find this image attractive? Why?

D37. Do you find this image attractive? Why?

D38. Do you find this image attractive? Why?

D39. When you look at these images, do you understand what happens, even if the characters/objects do not show themselves completely?

Yes

No

Do not know / No answer

D40. If you answered no, what do you see in the images?

D41. Observe and describe what you see in the following images

1

2

3

Section E: INTERPRETATION OF IMAGES

This section deals with a part of the reception that has to do mainly with subjectivity. It talks about the ability of the individuals to reveal what is sought and to build interpretative discourses from the observation. This point is especially relevant for our investigation.

E1. When you come across an image, do you try to understand with what intention it is made?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Several times
- 5. Almost always or always

E2. When you receive or consume an image, do you compare it with your own reality? Do you try to find a resemblance in your environment?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Several times
- 5. Almost always or always

E3. When you receive or consume an image, do you think about the way it was obtained (technically)?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Several times
- 5. Almost always or always

E4. When you look at an image, do you wonder about the characters/objects that appear in it?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Several times
- 5. Almost always or always

E5. Do you, generally, understand the intentions of the author of an image when you see it and share it?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Several times
- 5. Almost always or always

E6. Are you able to express verbally the emotions produced by an image you have seen?

- 1. Never
- 2. Very rarely
- 3. Occasionally
- 4. Several times
- 5. Almost always or always

E7. Do you think that images produced by men are different from those made by women?

- Yes
- No

E8. If you find differences, write which

E9. Do you think that in the creation of images work more women, or men?

- 1. More women than men
- 2. More men than women
- 3. Both equally
- 4. Do not know / No answer

E10. Do you know authors who work producing images?

- Yes
- No

E11. Give an example

Thank you for your collaboration! Greetings